

Changing Dynamics of European Migration Policies: The Case of Poland

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-06, 2024, p. 26– 56. - 0099-0001-2406-03003.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

1

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic* ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this* ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")

""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Article Application

Date: May 2024

Article

Publication Date: May 2024 Article Type: Review

Dr. Cüneyt Yılmaz

2

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

St. Clements
University Political
Sciences MSB

Orcid ID: 0000-0003-
1655-588X

[cuneytlmz53@gmail](mailto:cuneytlmz53@gmail.com)
[.com](mailto:cuneytlmz53@gmail.com)

Abstract

Migration has emerged as a significant focus point in contemporary global affairs and political discourse. Europe has encountered the need to reassess its migration policies, particularly in recent years, due to the escalating influx of migrants. This article analyzes the evolving dynamics of immigration policy in Europe, with a specific focus on the changes in Poland's immigration laws. Poland's history of hosting multiple waves of immigration has significantly influenced the development of its immigration policies. The article examines the alterations in immigration policies that occurred as a result of Poland's membership in the European Union. EU membership necessitated Poland to align its immigration policy with EU standards, prompting the government to adopt a more lenient stance on immigration. Nevertheless, the influx of refugees in Europe in 2015 led to a regression in Poland's immigration policies. The Polish government expressed opposition to letting refugees into the nation and implemented limits on immigrants. As a result of this circumstance, Poland is now questioning its adherence to the European Union's collective migration policies and is actively opposing the EU's plans for distributing refugees.

3

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Poland's evolving migration policies have had an impact on Europe's overall migration policies and sparked policy discussions inside the European Union. The case of Poland demonstrates that migration policies are influenced by both domestic preferences and global diplomatic interactions. The future impact of Poland's migration policies on the EU's general migration policies, as well as the evolution of the country's attitude in this field, will remain the central topic of academic and political discussions.

Keywords: Europe, migration policies, Poland, change, migration.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is a significant global concern, particularly in Europe, where it is the focus of political discussions. The waves of migration to Europe are complicated by the continent's historical and cultural variety, geographical position, and economic power. The intricate nature of the situation compels European Union countries to continuously devise and execute novel approaches in formulating and executing migration policies (Geddes, 2019). Central and Eastern European countries, particularly Poland, must align their migration policies with the overall policy of the European Union, while also considering their national interests (Grabowska, 2020). This article will use Poland as a case study to analyze the shifting dynamics of migration policies in Europe. It will explore how Poland's relationship with the European Union has influenced the development of its migration policies throughout time. Poland's migration policy has undergone significant changes due to notable events such as its entrance to the EU and the subsequent refugee crisis, as highlighted by Kutty (2018). The purpose of this essay is to analyze the intricate nature of Europe's migration policy, using Poland as a case study to illustrate this complexity.

AIM

CURRENT SCIENCE

This essay aims to analyze the evolving dynamics of Europe's migration policies using Poland as a case study. European Union (EU) member countries have varying views and practices when it comes to migration policies. Poland, a nation situated in Central and Eastern Europe that became a member of the European Union in 2004, has implemented significant modifications to its immigration laws. These changes have sparked extensive debates at both domestic and global levels. The primary aims of this investigation are:

Analyzing the historical context of Poland's immigration policies: What factors have influenced the development of Poland's immigration policies over time? What is the impact of historical events and periods on Poland's immigration policies?

Analyzing the Influence of EU Membership on Poland's Migration Policies: What impact has Poland's entrance to the EU had on the country's migration policies? What impact has Poland's participation in the EU had on its migration management and integration policies?

Analyzing the 2015 Refugee Crisis and the subsequent tightening of Poland's migration policies: What impact did the refugee crisis in 2015 have on Poland's migration policies? What were the decisions and procedures implemented by Poland during this time frame?

Analyzing the correlation between Poland's migration policies and the European Union: What is the relationship between Poland's migration policies and the EU's common migration policies and plans for distributing refugees? How has Poland's adherence or nonconformity to these policies influenced political discussions inside the EU?

This analysis will focus on the evolving dynamics of Poland's migration policies and assess their impact on migration policy throughout Europe. The objective is to gain a thorough comprehension of the migration management difficulties in Europe and how policy discrepancies among member nations are tackled, using Poland as an illustrative case. This article aims to analyze the evolving dynamics of Europe's migration policies by focusing on the case of Poland. European Union (EU) member countries have diverse views and practices when it comes to migration policies. Poland, a nation situated in Central and Eastern Europe that became a member of the European Union in 2004, has implemented significant modifications to its immigration laws. These changes have sparked extensive debates at both domestic and global levels. The primary aims of this study are:

Analyzing the historical context of Poland's immigration policies: What factors have

CURRENT SCIENCE

influenced the development of Poland's immigration policies over time? What impact have historical events and periods had on Poland's immigration policies? Analyzing the Influence of EU Membership on Poland's Migration Policies: What impact has Poland's membership in the EU had on the country's migration policies? What impact has EU membership had on Poland's migration management and integration policies? Analyzing the 2015 Refugee Crisis and the subsequent tightening of Poland's migration policies: What impact did the refugee crisis in Europe in 2015 have on Poland's migration policies? What were the decisions and practices implemented by Poland during this period? Analyzing the correlation between Poland's migration policies and the European Union: What is the relationship between Poland's stance on migration policy and the EU's common migration policies and plans for distributing refugees? How has Poland's adherence or nonconformity to these policies influenced political discussions inside the EU? This analysis will focus on the evolving dynamics of Poland's migration policies and assess their impact on migration policy throughout Europe. The objective is to gain a thorough comprehension of the migration management difficulties in Europe and how policy discrepancies among member nations are tackled, using Poland as an illustrative case. Migration is a significant global concern, particularly in Europe, where it is the focus of political discussions. The waves of migration to Europe are complicated by the continent's historical and cultural variety, geographical position, and economic power. The intricate nature of the situation compels European Union countries to continuously devise and execute novel approaches in formulating and executing migration policies (Geddes, 2019). Central and Eastern European countries, particularly Poland, must align their migration policies with the overall policy of the European Union, while also considering their national interests (Grabowska, 2020). This article will use Poland as a case study to analyze the shifting dynamics of Europe's migration policies and explore how Poland's relationship with the EU has been influenced, while also studying the development of its migration policies. Significant occurrences, such as Poland's entry into the EU and the subsequent refugee crisis, have served as crucial milestones in comprehending the extent to which Poland's migration policies have changed (Kuty, 2018). The purpose of this essay is to analyze the intricate nature

of Europe's migration policy and illustrate the functioning of this intricacy using the case study of Poland.

METHOD

This review article was compiled by conducting a systematic examination of the available literature to gain insight into and assess Poland's migration policies. The study employed the following methods:

A comprehensive literature review was conducted, analyzing academic publications, books, reports, and government documents pertaining to Poland's migration policies as well as the broader migration policies of the European Union. The sources were acquired from databases like Google Scholar, JSTOR, PubMed, and university libraries. A historical analysis was conducted on Poland's immigration policy, examining their growth over time and the modifications made during the process of joining the European Union. The analysis of historical events and periods focuses on the impact they had on Poland's immigration policies.

-Policy Analysis: An examination was conducted on the policies and actions implemented by Poland in response to the refugee crisis that occurred in 2015. This analysis focused on Poland's response to the European Union's collective migration policies and the strengthening of its own domestic migration laws.

A comparative analysis was conducted to analyze Poland's immigration policy in relation to the policies of other European Union member states. The purpose of these comparisons is to comprehend the disparities and assess the position of Poland's migration policies within the European Union.

Findings

CURRENT SCIENCE

Poland's encounters with post-World War II migratory waves and migration policies during the communist era have influenced the country's approach to managing migration (Grabowska, 2020).

During the post-Cold War era, there were noticeable alterations in immigration laws that coincided with the democratic movement in Poland. The EU's enlargement in 2004 resulted in substantial modifications to Poland's immigration rules. The European Union's principle of free movement has enabled Polish residents to migrate to other EU member states, resulting in a transformation of Poland's domestic migration policy (Kuty, 2018).

Polish citizens were given the privilege of unrestricted mobility between European Union countries following Poland's membership in the EU. Consequently, there was a substantial surge in the migration patterns of Polish individuals towards Western Europe. Specifically, England, Germany, Ireland, and the Netherlands have emerged as significant hubs for Polish immigrants (Kahanec & Zimmermann, 2010).

The integration of Poland into the European Union has provided Poles with expanded avenues for pursuing economic prospects. The prospect of higher earnings and improved living standards in Western Europe proved appealing to some Poles. Following their accession to the European Union, a considerable number of young and well-educated Polish individuals started to emigrate in search of more favorable employment prospects (Okólski, 2012). Poland's admission into the European Union necessitated the adjustment of its internal migration policies and regulations to conform to EU criteria. Poland underwent a process of restructuring its migration management and integration policies, bringing them in line with the European Union's common migration policy (Grabowska-Lusińska & Okólski, 2009). Poland has had to implement extensive legal and institutional modifications to its migration policies as a result of its membership in the European Union. Poland has implemented the EU's directives and regulations on migration, asylum, and border control by incorporating them into its national legislation.

Poland has harmonized its legislation on asylum applications and refugee rights with EU norms to adhere to the EU's migration and asylum policies. These modifications elevated the criteria in Poland's migration management and established regulations for the admission of refugees

(Frejka,

2008).

Poland has enhanced its border security and control measures as part of its accession to the Schengen Area, after its membership in the European Union. Poland has reorganized and upgraded its external borders in conformity with the European Union's common border security policy, as part of the Schengen Agreement (Kicinger, 2009). Poland's migration policy have been expedited in their alignment with EU criteria due to its membership in the EU. The 2015 refugee crisis resulted in a significant tightening of Poland's migration policies. The Polish government expressed opposition to the European Union's plans for distributing refugees and implemented limitations on accepting refugees (Geddes, 2019). Poland implemented exclusionary policies and propagated anti-immigrant rhetoric at this time. This scenario also impacted Poland's standing and relationships within the European Union. Poland's migration policy indicate its challenges in conforming to the European Union's unified migration rules. Poland's refusal to accept immigrants has undermined the notion of solidarity within the European Union and resulted in political strife (Castles, 2019). Poland's stringent position on migration policies has intensified scrutiny on the EU's management of migration policies and has had a significant impact on defining the EU's forthcoming migration policy. Poland's immigration policies should be evaluated in conjunction with the nation's historical experiences, political inclinations, and global circumstances. The efficient administration of these policies is crucial for the country's progress and the maintenance of social cohesion (Yentür, 2023). Research on the variety of political parties' orientations to the European Union in Poland reveals that various parties demonstrate distinct attitudes. The divergence between the appreciation for the European Union and the opposition towards it illustrates the intricate nature of the political environment in Poland (Taggart and Szczerbiak, 2001: 21). It is crucial to comprehend the varying attitudes that Poland has towards EU policies and the difficulties it encounters in its dealings with the EU. The diversity of political parties' stances towards the EU in Poland indicates the presence of

CURRENT SCIENCE

multiple political perspectives in the country and the intricate nature of its interactions with the EU (Tagart and Szczerbiak, 2001: 18). For instance, the Catholic nationalist Christian National Unity Party and the Polish Peasants' Party expressed doubt towards the EU, as stated by Tagart and Szczerbiak (2001: 18). On the other hand, the Union of Polish Families and the Defense Party took a stance against the EU, according to Önkol (2009). Nevertheless, perspectives on the European Union have evolved throughout time and are contingent upon political advancements. The Law and Justice Party's endorsement of EU membership during the 2001 elections demonstrates the party's changing stance, as documented by Önkol (2009). Poland's political inclinations have been significantly influenced by attitudes towards the EU. During the 2001 elections, it was seen that the majority of parties were in favor of supporting the EU candidacy (Szczerbiak, 2002: 13-18). Nevertheless, the cautious approach of parties like the Law and Justice Party towards EU membership, and their insistence on certain conditions, highlights the political variety inside the country (Szczerbiak, 2002: 15). These sentiments have played a crucial role in shaping Poland's ties with the EU and have heightened the EU's apprehension about the exploitation of the country's resources (Szczerbiak, 2002: 15). The 2004 European Parliament elections in Poland mirrored the discussions in Polish politics, and there was a rise in opposition to the European Union within the country (Millard, 2010: 124). Nevertheless, the endorsement of EU integration by parties like Civic Platform highlights the variety within the political sphere (Millard, 2010: 134). This underscores the intricacy of Poland's relations with the EU and the potential divergence of political inclinations. Poland's political parties have undergone a transformation in their stance towards the European Union (EU) over the years. For instance, during the 2007 legislative elections, there was a noticeable contrast between the Law and Justice Party's statist policies and the Civil Platform's economic liberal policies, as well as their differing perspectives on the European Union (Millard, 2010: 159). The heterogeneity observed in Poland's relations with the EU is a direct result of the intricate and diverse range of political inclinations. The 2014 European Parliament elections held significant symbolic significance for Poland and brought attention to EU-related matters (Lodzki and Paluch, 2017: 43). Nevertheless, the criticism of EU policies and resistance to energy policy by right-wing populist parties in the country covers a range of opinions (Lodzki and Paluch, 2017: 20, 21).

CURRENT SCIENCE

The Law and Justice Party, which experienced a defeat in the parliamentary elections of 2011, was under the leadership of Jarosław Kaczyński. He assumed power alongside Kaczyński in the elections of 2015. Nevertheless, the party's adversarial stance towards the European Union remains unchanged (BBC, 2015). This position demonstrates that the opposing and endorsing factions of the EU in Poland are evenly matched. The growing criticism of the European Union in Poland stems from various factions within the country expressing their opposition to EU policy. The public's perception of the EU has become more critical due to the belief that it fails to safeguard national interests and that political parties in the country are unwaveringly devoted to the EU. According to opinion polls conducted in 2019, faith in the European Union (EU) is declining in Poland, while the belief that the EU is encountering multiple issues is growing stronger (BBC, 2019; European Commission, 2019). This scenario exemplifies the intricacy of Poland's interactions with the European Union and the nation's stance on EU policy. The Law and Justice Party's rise to power in Poland during the 2015 elections resulted in a significant political change in the country (Buras, 2017). This transition has particularly been evident in the departure from the idea of separation of powers and the scrutiny of the autonomy of the judiciary. The current scenario has resulted in strained ties with the EU and heightened apprehensions regarding the nation's democratic norms (Buras, 2017). The primary cause of political difficulties between the EU and Poland is centered around issues such as the autonomy of the Constitutional Court and the implementation of judicial reforms (Buras, 2017). The European Union has urged Poland to uphold democratic principles and safeguard the autonomy of the judicial system. Nevertheless, the Polish government disregarded these concerns and proceeded with its reforms, thereby exacerbating the strain in its relations with the EU (Buras, 2017). Poland's choice to abstain from joining the Eurozone has resulted in a divergent stance on fiscal policies inside the European Union (Schimmelfennig, 2017). The nation opted for this decision in order to safeguard its domestic currency and retain its economic autonomy. This scenario is a significant determinant impacting the economic and political equilibrium inside the EU (Schimmelfennig, 2017). Poland's migration and refugee policies exacerbate the split inside the EU (Hooghe and Marks,

CURRENT SCIENCE

2019). The nation prioritizes safeguarding its national identity and sovereignty through the implementation of a stringent approach towards immigration and refugees. This approach is not compatible with the European Union's common migration policies and puts a pressure on the relations between the European Union and Poland (Hooghe and Marks, 2019). Poland is endeavoring to enhance its standing inside the European Union by means of regional cooperation projects (Zwolski, 2017). The Three Seas Initiative and similar projects seek to enhance the country's regional dominance and sway within the European Union. Nevertheless, these attempts have the potential to undermine the unity and coherence of the European Union and lead to fragmentation in its foreign policy (Zwolski, 2017). Poland's financial integration into the European Union (EU) encounters notable obstacles, including the transfer of the country's financial sovereignty and adjustment to the Euro currency. This scenario involves the process of aligning Poland's financial policies with the criteria set by the European Union, while also raising worries about potential negative impacts on the EU's monetary union (Ingham and Ingham, 2002: 11, 12). Poland's integration of the Euro has emerged as a key concern on the political agenda since 2008. Nevertheless, the worldwide economic crisis and the Euro crisis in late 2008 had a detrimental impact on this progression (Kierzenkowski, 2010: 6, 7). Poland decided to delay its transition to the Euro due to the impact of exchange rate fluctuations and inflation pressure (Kierzenkowski, 2010: 6, 7). The agriculture sector of Poland holds a significant role in its interactions with the European Union. The single agricultural policy of the European Union is a significant determinant of Poland's agriculture policy (IKV, 2011). During Poland's EU presidency, there was a notable focus on calls for changes in agricultural policy and the allocation of direct payments (IKV, 2011).

The Law and Justice Party in Poland is influenced by the country's internal political dynamics when it comes to their stance on EU policy (Hodson and Puetter, 2019: 10, 11). Party leader Kaczynski expressed both criticism towards the EU and highlighted the significance of integration (Hodson and Puetter, 2019: 10, 11). Nevertheless, accusations of the EU's infringement against democratic norms in Poland have caused tension in EU ties (Hodson and Puetter, 2019: 10, 11; European Commission, 2017b).

12

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Historical Background of the European Union's Migration Policies

Europe, Part Two. It had three primary waves of migration following World War II. The initial wave consisted of labor migration occurring from 1950 to 1970. Nevertheless, as European countries saw economic growth in the mid-1970s, they implemented policies aimed at incentivizing migrant workers to go back to their countries of origin (Ölmez Kıyıcı and Kaygısız, 2018). Nevertheless, the enforcement of these regulations resulted in a subsequent surge of migration as migrant workers facilitated the arrival of their families via family reunification. Following the conclusion of the Cold War, a third surge of migration occurred, consisting of refugees and asylum seekers.

EU member states have typically formulated their migration policies through intergovernmental agreements. Nevertheless, progress was made in the creation of a unified migration strategy by the signing of the Maastricht Treaty in 1993 and the Schengen Agreement in 1995 (Koca, 2002). These accords encompassed provisions about the safeguarding of the European Union's external borders and shared concerns pertaining to migration. Nevertheless, these rules primarily prioritize security and have faced criticism. The Amsterdam Agreement, negotiated in 1997 and implemented in 1999, enhanced the harmonization of migration rules among EU member states. The purpose of this agreement is to safeguard the external borders of the EU and offer international protection to refugees (Saraçlı, 2019). During this period, the European Union's migration policies prioritized justice and freedom over security. The Lisbon Treaty, ratified in 2007, established the legal framework for the European Union's migration strategy. The purpose of this agreement is to efficiently administer the migration policies of the European Union and establish collaboration among member states (Ölmez Kıyıcı and Kaygısız, 2018). Nevertheless, the migratory crises that occurred in subsequent years posed challenges for the European Union in formulating a coherent migration policy and led to divergent viewpoints among member states.

European Integration and Migration Policies

European Integration is the process of combining political, economic, and social aspects of Europe into a unified entity. The primary objective of the organization is to enhance international collaboration in Europe and guarantee peace and prosperity among European nations. The historical origins of European Integration arose as a response to the instability and fragmentation of Europe in the aftermath of the Second World War. The primary objectives of European Integration encompass the amalgamation of economies, political collaboration, unhindered mobility, and the dissemination of shared values. In order to accomplish these objectives, the institutions and agreements formed among various European nations play a crucial role. The European Union (EU) is a very influential and efficient entity in the process of European integration.

The process of European Integration is characterized by the establishment of legally binding agreements referred to as the Fundamental Founding Treaties. These accords have facilitated the development and implementation of shared policies across numerous domains in Europe (Hooghe and Marks, 2019). The Treaties of Rome were a significant milestone in the creation of the European Economic Community (EEC) and the economic unification of Europe (Van Elsas, Hakhverdian, & van der Brug, 2016). The advancement of European Integration has evolved through two primary mechanisms: enlargement and consolidation. The term "enlargement process" pertains to the act of expanding Europe by admitting new members, whereas the term "deepening process" refers to the strengthening of Europe's integration among its current members (Kriesi, Grande, Lachat, Dolezal, Bornschier, & Frey, 2006). These processes were significant in shaping the political, economic, and social structure of Europe (according to Schimmelfennig, 2014). The present state of European Integration exhibits an intricate and multifaceted framework. The European Union's institutions, policies, and intergovernmental relations are crucial factors that influence the process of European Integration (Stubb, 1996). In addition, the worldwide problems and shifting geopolitical dynamics that Europe is currently experiencing have a

CURRENT SCIENCE

considerable influence on the future of European Integration (Holzinger and Schimmelfennig, 2012).

Immigration policies play a significant role in both Europe's domestic and foreign politics. The EU's migration policy has been significantly influenced by the rise in migratory movements, particularly in recent years. The primary concerns on the EU's policy agenda revolve around the integration, adaptation, and protection of immigrants. Integration theories play a significant role in shaping migration policies in Europe. The theory of Differentiated Integration offers a significant foundation for comprehending the process of European integration. This theory elucidates the process of EU integration occurring at varying paces and in diverse domains. For instance, within the EU's internal market, economic regions that experience more rapid free movement exhibit a higher degree of integration compared to other regions.

Furthermore, theories such as Neo-Functionalism and Post-Functionalism help enhance the comprehension of the European Union's migration policies. These theories elucidate the factors that influence the formation of migration policies by examining the individuals, motivations, and dynamics involved in the EU's policy-making process. Neo-Functionalism posits that the European Union formulates migration policies by fostering collaboration among diverse interest groups.

A comprehension of the integration process is enhanced by considering the historical context of migration policies in Europe. Migration policies have been a significant realm of collaboration and disagreement among member states since the foundation of the EU. The signing of the Schengen Agreement has brought attention to important matters concerning the freedom of movement within the EU's internal borders and the protection of its external borders, which have become central to migration policies. European Integration and Migration Policies play a significant role in the process of integrating Europe. To comprehend the actors and interactions in the EU's policy-making process, it is necessary to employ multiple theories. Furthermore, the historical context of migration policies has a significant role in establishing the European Union's present policy agenda (Yentür, 2023).

Historical Background of Poland's Migration Policies

Poland's migration policies are influenced by its geographical location, political history, and socioeconomic growth. Poland has had several boundary modifications throughout its history and has confronted wars and political regime alterations. This predicament has led to a continuous evolution of the country's immigration policies. Poland's migration policies are intricately connected to the nation's historical, political, and economic dynamics. Within this framework, the development of Poland's migration policies, particularly in the aftermath of World War II. It was influenced by momentous events such as shifts in population demographics after World War II, the alteration of political systems, and the joining of the European Union. II. After World War II, Poland experienced significant population relocation and the reconfiguration of its borders. Large numbers of Polish citizens were compelled to migrate to Germany and the Soviet Union, resulting in a significant alteration to the demographic composition of the country (Davies, 2005). This process was the initial significant milestone in Poland's immigration policies. During the aftermath of the war, Poland fell under the sway of the Soviet Union, which established a communist regime. During this period, migration occurred with stringent government regulation, and there was a heightened focus on accepting political refugees and immigrants from the East (Stola, 2001). Poland's migration policy during the Cold War were influenced by the overall policies of the Eastern Bloc. Nevertheless, Polish individuals seeking refuge from political constraints relocated to Western countries, and the nation welcomed immigration from other countries within the Eastern Bloc (Kamesella, 2008). The dissolution of the communist regime in 1989 triggered a substantial overhaul of Poland's immigration laws. As a result of the democratic process, the ability of Polish citizens to emigrate to other countries increased, leading to a significant influx of immigrants to Western Europe and North America. Poland began the process of joining the European Union during this time, and its membership in the EU caused significant changes to its migration policies (Iglicka, 2001; Kahanec & Zimmermann, 2010). Poland has to conform its migration policies

16

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

to EU norms as a condition of EU membership, leading to a restructuring of its migration management and integration policies (Grabowska, 2020). The historical context of Poland's immigration policies is a manifestation of the political and economic transformations that the country has undergone in the past. II. Poland's migration policies have undergone continuous changes, starting from displacements in the post-World War II era, followed by immigration restrictions during the communist regime, and then transitioning to free migration due to the democratization process. Furthermore, Poland has experienced a rise in international migration flows with its EU membership. Gaining a historical perspective is crucial for comprehending Poland's present immigration policies and its stance within the European Union. Poland's migration policy have undergone substantial modifications both prior to and following its accession to the European Union (EU). These developments are intricately connected to the country's historical experiences and global circumstances. Prior to its accession to the European Union, Poland was subject to the dominance of the Soviet Union under a communist state. Immigration occurred under stringent government regulation, and measures were implemented to restrict migration to the Western regions. Nevertheless, immigrants originating from the Eastern regions were welcomed, with a particular emphasis on political refugees and Jewish immigrants who sought sanctuary in Poland. Following the downfall of the communist system in 1989, the process of democratization commenced in Poland. During this time, the liberty of Polish residents to migrate to other countries increased, leading Poles to seek improved living conditions in Western Europe and North America. The EU's expansion in 2004 brought about a profound transformation in Poland's immigration policies. EU membership has facilitated the unrestricted mobility of Polish individuals across Europe, resulting in a notable surge in Polish migration to other EU nations (Yentür, 2023).

As part of the EU membership process, Poland has to align its migration management and integration policies with the standards set by the EU. This procedure primarily emphasizes the adaptation to the European Union's unified migration rules and the facilitation of immigrant integration. Subsequent to joining the European Union, there has been a noticeable rise in

biases and marginalization towards immigrants in Poland. Specifically, the negative perspective is often attributed to economic consequences, such as immigrants exerting downward pressure on the wages of the local workers.

Poland's Accession to the EU and Change in Migration Policies

Poland's entry into the European Union (EU) has resulted in profound and intricate transformations in the nation's political, economic, and social frameworks. The commencement of this process occurred in the late 1990s and expedited the nation's shift towards democratization and a market-based economy. Poland enacted extensive reforms during the process of entrance negotiations in order to fulfill the political and economic criteria set by the EU. The changes encompass various domains, including upholding the principles of legal governance, developing a market-based economic system, fortifying democratic institutions, and safeguarding human rights (Schimmelfennig and Winzen, 2019; Kochenov, 2015). The integration of Poland into the European Union has resulted in substantial transformations in the nation's domestic policy and social framework. Poland expedited the process of democratization and aligned its economic structures with EU norms by implementing EU standards (Henderson, 2015). Nevertheless, Poland also developed a discerning perspective towards the EU at this time. According to Kochenov (2015), there is a contention that being a member of the EU diminishes the authority of Poland as a nation and puts its interests at risk. The EU's expansion to include Poland has resulted in substantial alterations to the nation's migration laws. Poland's accession to the EU resulted in the removal of border restrictions, allowing for unrestricted mobility between Poland and other EU member states. Consequently, this led to a rise in the number of immigrants residing in Poland (Grabowska-Lusinska and Okolski, 2014). Following its admission to the EU, the Polish government has implemented several measures to bring its migration policy in line with EU norms (Triandafyllidou, 2013).

These phases involve implementing initiatives to facilitate the assimilation of immigrants, addressing unauthorized immigration, and safeguarding the social entitlements of immigrants (Grabowska-Lusinska and Okolski, 2014). Nevertheless, discussions regarding immigration restrictions have escalated in Poland in recent years. Specifically, the Polish government, which holds a skeptical stance towards the European Union's migration policy, has implemented more stringent measures to restrict migration to their country and safeguard the EU's external borders.

Poland's entry into the EU resulted in substantial modifications to immigration rules, which in turn had notable social and political consequences. The migration of individuals from Poland to Western Europe resulted in significant demographic shifts within the country. The emigration of a segment of the youthful and well-educated populace has resulted in alterations in the labor market in Poland and led to labor scarcities in certain places (White, 2011). Nevertheless, it also had a role in the expansion of the Polish economy and the enhancement of welfare. Alterations in immigration rules have additionally sparked discussions in the realm of domestic politics in Poland. In certain quarters, the process of conforming to the European Union's unified migration rules was seen as a relinquishment of national autonomy, leading to an increase in anti-EU rhetoric (Buchowski, 2006). Following the 2015 refugee crisis, Poland has witnessed a surge in anti-immigrant policies and rhetoric. The EU's membership of Poland has had a profound impact on not only the country's immigration policy, but also on all aspects of its policies and social structure as a whole. Poland benefits much in terms of economics, society, and politics by being a member of the EU. However, it also has obligations when it comes to migration regulations. Poland has received substantial financial resources for economic development and infrastructural developments as a result of its membership in the European Union. According to Inotai (2009), these monies contributed to the rapid economic growth of Poland and improved the level of living. Poland's EU membership grants it the chance to actively engage in the EU's decision-making

CURRENT SCIENCE

procedures and contribute to policy-making processes. As a result, Poland gained more influence in the global stage (Górka, 2013).

Poland's entry into the European Union has prompted the government to implement extensive and substantial modifications to its migration policies. EU membership has provided Poles with new opportunities, but it has also necessitated higher standards in managing migration and faster adjustment to the EU's common rules. Nevertheless, this approach also sparked social and political controversies.

Poland's Refugee Crisis and Hardening in Migration Policies

The refugee crisis that impacted Europe in 2015 sparked significant political and social discussions in Poland, as well as in several other European Union (EU) member nations. After the crisis, Poland implemented stricter migration laws and firmly expressed its stance on the EU's common refugee policies (Sadowski, 2016). Several primary factors have led to the reinforcement of Poland's immigration laws. The Polish administration has expressed apprehension regarding the potential security issues that may arise from a significant influx of refugees (Sadowski, 2016). Specifically, the heightened threat of terrorism and extremism has amplified popular apprehensions regarding the acceptance of refugees. In addition, Poland possesses a socially homogeneous structure, and the government has contended that extensive immigration might potentially undermine social cohesiveness and cultural integrity. Consequently, there has been a widespread adoption of a pessimistic outlook, particularly directed against Muslim refugee communities (Górak-Sosnowska, 2016). Poland's refugee policies have been impacted by political and ideological forces. The ruling Law and Justice Party (PiS) is particularly recognized for its nationalist and conservative policies. Through the utilization of anti-refugee rhetoric, PiS managed to garner support in local politics while simultaneously questioning the refugee policies of the EU (Bill, 2016). Poland's uncompromising position on the refugee problem has resulted in strained relations with the European Union. Poland was a prominent opponent of the EU's proposal for a quota

CURRENT SCIENCE

system, which aimed to achieve an equitable distribution of refugees among member states (Trauner, 2016). Poland's resistance to the quota system has resulted in legal and political disputes with the European Union. The European Union has commenced infringement processes against Poland and other countries in the Visegrád Group (Hungary, Czech Republic, and Slovakia). The EU is demanding that these nations meet their obligations with regards to admitting refugees (Kořan, 2018).

The consequences of the refugee crisis have also been apparent in Poland's domestic politics. The government has implemented stricter restrictions and adopted more forceful language against refugees, resulting in a rise in popular hostility towards refugees (Buchowski, 2017). The PiS government has fostered an unfavorable public impression of refugees through the utilization of anti-refugee rhetoric. In addition, the government has implemented stricter legal requirements for the acceptance of refugees and asylum seekers and has intensified border controls (Kucharczyk & Mesežnikov, 2015). Poland has implemented measures to impede the entry of migrants into the nation by imposing stringent requirements for refugee applications. These initiatives are tangible manifestations of the strengthening of refugee policies (Kucharczyk & Mesežnikov, 2015). These reasons have influenced Poland's reaction to the refugee crisis and the strengthening of migration policies, leading to problems in the country's relations with the EU.

Poland's stringent reaction to the refugee crisis has resulted in substantial alterations to the nation's immigration policies. Poland's stance towards refugees is mostly influenced by security and cultural adaption considerations. This sentiment also had an impact on the country's internal politics and led to the reinforcement of anti-refugee rhetoric (Sadowski, 2016). The Polish government's resistance to large-scale refugee influxes was primarily driven by security concerns, particularly in relation to the possibility of terrorism and extremism (Sadowski, 2016). Cultural adaption challenges have played a significant role in shaping Poland's approach to the refugee crisis. Poland, known for its socially homogeneous structure, has resisted accepting migrants due to concerns that widespread immigration could have a detrimental impact on social cohesion and cultural integrity (Górak-Sosnowska, 2016). Nevertheless, the strain in Poland's relations with the European Union extends beyond the

refugee issue. Poland's choice to oppose the European Union's refugee policies and reject the quota system has had a detrimental impact on its relations with other EU members (Trauner, 2016). Poland's position inside the EU was undermined by this circumstance, leading to worldwide criticism. The initiation of infringement actions by the EU against Poland and other Visegrád Group nations is one of the elements that impact Poland's status inside the EU (Kořan, 2018).

Poland's robust reaction to the refugee crisis has had a profound impact on the nation's internal and external policies. This scenario has also influenced the country's interactions with the EU and prompted worldwide discussions on adjustments in migration rules.

Immigration and Asylum Policies Differentiating Between EU Member States

The variations in immigration and asylum policy among European Union member countries are a multifaceted matter influenced by the internal dynamics of the bloc and the individual countries' domestic policies. The variations stem from the historical, cultural, economic, and political disparities among the nations. Certain EU member states possess larger and more affluent economies, hence providing greater prospects for immigrants, whilst others possess smaller economies and less resources, resulting in more stringent immigration regulations. For instance, nations with substantial economies like Germany and France have the capacity to offer immigrants a wider range of career prospects and social welfare programs, whereas countries with smaller economies may have more constraints in these areas.

Furthermore, the cultural disparities among immigrants and variations in the perception of integration procedures among EU member nations also exert a significant influence. Certain nations implement diverse strategies to promote the assimilation of immigrants, whilst others may enforce more stringent border controls and integration policies. Conversely, migration and refugee policies can also be influenced by domestic policies and the political climate in some nations. Specifically, governments that embrace extremist right-wing

CURRENT SCIENCE

or left-wing ideologies may implement more stringent or lenient immigration laws. The variations in migration and asylum policy among EU member countries can be attributed to economic, cultural, and political causes. It is important to remember that these disparities might lead to tensions among member nations and pose challenges in reaching a consensus (Yentür, 2023).

In recent years, the migration policies of the European Union (EU) have experienced substantial modifications, which have had an impact on how EU countries handle the receipt, distribution, and integration of immigrants (Sadowski, 2019). In 2024, European Union government ministers approved ten legal chapters of the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, which serves as the most recent illustration of these changes. Nevertheless, the opposition of certain nations, including Poland, to this decision highlights the disparities in migration policies and political disputes inside the bloc.

Poland has historically implemented stringent immigration regulations and maintains a critical stance towards the European Union's migration policies (Sadowski, 2019). The opposition of Hungary and Poland to the package highlights divergent perspectives and conflicting interests over migration policies inside the union. It is crucial to comprehend Poland's impact within the European Union and its involvement in determining migration policies. Poland's stringent position on immigration and asylum regulations is intricately linked to the nation's internal political dynamics. Specifically, in Poland, there is a considerable influence of populist and nationalist rhetoric that supports strict measures targeting immigrants (Kucharczyk & Mesežnikov, 2015). The Polish government is in opposition to the immigration policy of the European Union, placing emphasis on national sovereignty and security. In conclusion,

The evolving dynamics of Poland's migration policy serve as a significant illustration within the broader framework of the European Union's migration management. Poland's adoption of a more stringent policy stance towards immigrants in recent years has had significant and conclusive impacts on immigration policies, both within the country and throughout Europe. This adjustment in Poland's migration policies is significant as it offers a viewpoint in dealing with the complexities of migration management in the European Union and the divergences in

CURRENT SCIENCE

policies across member states. The recent shift towards stricter migration rules in Poland has added difficulty to the establishment and implementation of the European Union's common migration policies.

Poland's stance has the potential to impact the broader perspective of the European Union's migration and asylum policies. Other member states have the option to adopt the more stringent policy approach implemented by Poland or further restrict their own immigration rules. This position may provide challenges in achieving the harmonization of the European Union's migration and asylum policy and the establishment of a unified approach. The shifting dynamics of Poland's migration policies are a significant focal point in the European Union's broader efforts to regulate migration. Poland's adoption of a more stringent policy approach should be regarded as a crucial factor in formulating and executing migration policies, both inside the country and throughout Europe. This scenario prompts significant inquiries regarding the future trajectories and relevance of the European Union's migration and asylum policy.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted and published in the literature.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Support: The authors reported no use of financial support related to this article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Publication ethics of magazine; scientific research and

publications are based on fundamental principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others.

aims to ensure that it is carried out in accordance with the principles and for this to happen,

It is a national-based scientific organization that aims to achieve these principles in the field of social sciences is a magazine. The criteria of the Declaration of Helsinki were considered.

RESOURCES

Books:

Castles, S. (2019). Migration and global politics. Cambridge University Press.

Geddes, A. (2019). Migration and immigration: A global view. ABC-CLIO.

Grabowska, I. (2020). Poland and the European Union: The Puzzle of Restitution Policies. Routledge.

Kuty, Ł. (2018). Poland's European Policy: Top-Down Approach. Routledge.

Davies, N. (2005). God's Playground: A History of Poland. Oxford University Press.

Stola, D. (2001). Jewish emigration from Communist Poland: The Decline of Polish Jewry in the Aftermath of the Holocaust East European Jewish Affairs.

Kamusella, T. (2008). The Politics of Language and Nationalism in Modern Central Europe. Palgrave Macmillan.

Iglicka, K. (2001). Poland's Post-War Dynamics of Migration. Ashgate.

Kahanec, M., & Zimmermann, K. F. (2010). Migration in an Enlarged EU: A Challenging Solution? Springer.

Buchowski, M. (2006). The Specter of orientalism in Europe: From exotic others to stigmatized brother anthropological Quarterly, 79(3), 463-482.

Frejka, T. (2008). Overview Chapter 9: International Migration in Central and Eastern Europe and Its Impact on Regional Demographic Development. International Migration in Central and Eastern Europe. United Nations.

Górka, M. (2013). Poland's role in the decision-making process in the European Union: Current state and prospects. Yearbook of Polish European Studies, 16, 9-32.

Yentür, D (2023). Migration and International Migration, Zet Academic Publications.

Articles and Reviews:

Akgül Açıkmese, S. (2004). European Integration in the Light of International Relations Theories. International Relations, 1(1), 1-32.

Andersen, S. S., & Sitter, N. (2006). Differentiated Integration: What is it and How Much Can the EU Accommodate? European Integration, 28(4), 313-330.

BBC. (2019). Most EU citizens believe that the EU may disintegrate within 10-20 years. <https://www.bbc.com/turkce/haberler-dunya-48293768>

BBC. (2015). Poland elections: Conservatives secure decisive win. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-34631826>

Braun, M. (2020). Postfunctionalism, Identity and the Visegrad Group. Journal of Common Market Studies, 58(4), 925-940.

Buras, P. (2017). Europe and Its Discontents: Poland's Collision Course with the European Union. European Council on Foreign Affairs Relations.

Euronews. (2017). Poland is uncomfortable with the European Union. <https://tr.euronews.com/2017/09/13/polonya-avrupa-birligi-nden-rahatsiz>

European Commission. (2019). Public opinion in the European Union. Standard Eurobarometer 92.

European Commission. (2017a). Poland: CAP in your country.

European Commission. (2017b). Rule of Law: European Commission acts to defend judicial independence in Poland.

European Union. (2020). Poland: Overview.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2014). Poland Common Agricultural Policies.

European Commission. (2014). Factsheet on 2014-2020 Rural Development Program for Poland.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2014). Poland Common Agricultural Policies.

Gänzle, S., Leruth, B., & Trondal, J. (2020). Differentiation, integration and disintegration in a post-Brexit era. Routledge.

Henderson, K., & Robinson, N. (1997). Post-Communist Politics: An Introduction. Prentice Hall Europe.

Hodson, D., & Puetter, U. (2019). The European Union in disequilibrium: New intergovernmentalism, postfunctionalism and integration theory in the post-Maastricht period. Journal of European Public Politics, 1-20.

- Holzinger, K., & Schimmelfennig, F. (2012). Differentiated Integration in the European Union: Many Concepts, Sparse Theory, Few Data. *Journal of European Public Politics*, 19(2), 292-305.
- Hooghe, L., & Marks, G. (2019). Grand theories of European integration in the twenty-first century. *Journal of European Public Politics*, 26(8), 1113-1133.
- Hooghe, L., & Marks, G. (2018). Cleavage theory meets Europe's crises: Lipset, Rokkan, and the transnational cleavage. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 25(1), 109-135.
- Hooghe, L., & Marks, G. (2008). A Postfunctionalist Theory of European Integration: From permissive consensus to Constraining Dissensus. *British Journal of Political Science*, 39(1), 1-23.
- Hutter, S., & Kriesi, H. (2019). Politicizing Europe in times of crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(7), 996-1017.
- IKV. (2011). Reform of the Common Agricultural Policy is among Poland's priorities. *E-Bulletin*, 4-10 July 2011.
- Ingham, H., & Ingham, M. (2002). Towards a United Europe. EU Expansion to the East: Prospects and Problems, 1-23.
- Karasinska-Fendler, M., Skotnicka-Illasiewicz, E., Sobotka, K., & Swierkocki, J. (two thousand). Poland. Winners' and Losers of EU Integration: Policy Issues for Central and Eastern Europe, 162-189.

Book Chapters:

- Ölmez Kılıcı, S., & Kaygısız, B. (2018). Economic Migration and Integration Process from Turkey to Germany. In E. Özbay, B. Erdem, & A. Güler (Eds.), *Migration and Immigration: Global and Local Dynamics* (pp. 469-484). Literaturk Publications.

Reports and Internet Resources:

Ministry of National Defense. (2020). european Union missions' oath operations.
<https://www.gov.pl/web/national-defence/eu-missions-and-operations>

OECD. (2018). Country statistical profile: Poland 2018. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/csp-pol-table-2018-4-en>

Poland In. (2018). Poland wants equal EU payments for farmers: Minister.
<https://polandin.com/37474770/poland-wants-equal-eu-payments-for-farmers-minister>

Przegon, W. (2009). Polish country versus common agricultural policy in the EU. *Polska academy Nauk*, (7), 37-46.

Rucinski, P. (2017). Poland's priorities for Common Agricultural Policies after 2020. *Global Agricultural Information Network (GAIN) Report*.

Schimmelfennig, F. (2017). differentiation and Self- determination in European Integration. *Euborders working Paper 01*.

Schimmelfennig, F. (2014a). European Integration in the Euro Crisis: The Limits of Postfunctionalism. *Journal of European Integration*, 36(3), 321-337.

Schimmelfennig, F. (2014b). EU enlargement oath differentiated integration: Discrimination or equal treatment? *Journal of Europe public Politics*, 21(5), 681-698.

Van Elsas, E. J., Hakhverdian, A., & van der Brug, W. (2016). United against a common foe? the nature oath origins of Euroscepticism among left-wing oath right-wing citizens *West European Politics*, 39(6), 1181–1204.

Verhelst, S. (2013). A Beginner's Guide to Differentiated Integration in the EU; Variable geometry Union: How Differentiated Integration is Shaping theEU. *studio Diplomatica*, 66(3), 7-18.

- Webb, P., & Lewis, P. G. (1998). the lessons of comparative politics: Russian politics parties as independent variables? the Journal of Communist Studies oath Transition Politics, 14(1-2), 253-264.
- Webber, D. (2019). Trends in Europe political (dis) integration. An analysis of postfunctionalist oath other explanations. Journal of Europe public Politics, 26(8), 1134-1152.
- Wells, A. (2018). What Europeans think are the most critical issues facing theEU. <https://yougov.co.uk/topics/politics/articles-reports/2018/05/11/yougov-data-reveals-what-europeans-think-are-most->
- Winzen, T. (2020). Government Euroscepticism oath differentiated integration. Journal of Europe public Politics, 1-19.
- Wnuk-Lipinski, E. (2001). How has Polish society Changed since 1989? implications for the New Decade. In G. Blazyca & R. Rapacki (Eds.), Poland into the New Millennium, 54-72.
- Zwolski, K. (2017). Poland's Foreign Policy Turn. Survival, 59(4), 167-182.
- <https://tr.euronews.com/my-europe/2024/05/14/ab-polonya-ve-macaristanin-karsi-oyuna-ragmen-goc-anlasmasini-onayladi> (15.05.2024)